

IMPLEMENTING CHARACTER EDUCATION IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE LEARNING IN HIGHER EDUCATION

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ANNOTATION: This article provides information about character education, its definition, and some very common ways of implementation character education in English learning process.

KEY WORDS: social behavior, education industry, analytical approach, civic values.

I. INTRODUCTION

Character education is the process by which people learn to interact with society, usually by teaching basic virtues such as courage, justice, and wisdom. Emotions, thoughts, and actions work together to form character. Character education is the act of teaching students to transform these feelings, thoughts, and behaviors into social behavior[1]. Character education is the training of children and adults in ways that help them develop morally, civilly, well-behaved, well-behaved, non-violently, healthy, critical, successful, traditional, obedient or unique. is a common term to describe teaching. socially acceptable beings. Current and past concepts under the term include social and emotional learning, moral reasoning and cognitive development, life skills training, health education, violence prevention, critical thinking, ethical reasoning, conflict resolution, and mediation. Most of them are now considered to be failed programs, that is, "religious education", "moral development", "clarification of values". Today, there are dozens of character education programs in schools and businesses fighting for acceptance. Some are commercial, some are nonprofit, and many are uniquely developed by states, districts, and schools. The general approach of these programs

is to provide a list of principles, pillars, values, or virtues that are memorized or thematic activities are planned. It is usually claimed that the values included in any particular list are universally accepted. However, there is no agreement among competing programs on the core values (eg, honesty, stewardship, kindness, generosity, courage, freedom, justice, equality, and respect) or even how many. There are also no common or standard tools for evaluating, implementing, or evaluating programs [2].

II. METHODS

Character education is generally understood as a specific approach aimed at developing desirable character traits in students at all levels of education through formal and non-formal educational activities. However, it has been defined in different ways from different perspectives. For example, it is understood as an approach to moral and value education [3], as well as a process of character formation through the education of moral and good values. Character education is closely related to the concept of moral and values education, which is broader in scope and less clear about what constitutes character education [3]. Character usually represents a set of interrelated personal values that guide our behavior and define who we are and whom we relate to; it is composed of three integral moral aspects, namely moral knowledge, moral feeling and moral attitude. When translated into actual behavior, it is called values. Virtues are strong character traits associated with morally commendable behavior in specific areas of a person's life [4].

III. RESULTS

Values-based knowledge and skills contribute to students' well-being by enhancing their academic achievement and social and emotional development, as well as empowering them to better deal with the challenges they face. Although older college students are generally more fully developed on moral dimensions than younger students, this is not necessarily true because the developmental variables are age-related rather than educational-level. Therefore, there is still great

potential to improve the moral qualities of college students, including values, goals, and attitudes; these changes continue after college. Colby argued that education is not complete until students not only acquire knowledge, but are also able to use that knowledge to act responsibly. However, the "education industry", supported by narrow professional training that does not value the humanities, has led to a shift towards efficiency and economic responsibility. This has reduced the space for moral and ethical dimensions and may weaken higher education's ability to train "thoughtful, engaged citizens and honest and ethical scholars"[5]. He argues that if higher education is to produce graduates who can be responsible citizens with good character or virtues, then "to act in the world a full account of one's ability and a decision to do so wisely". This competence goes far beyond professional competence and includes consideration of judgments, evaluation of both ends and means, and the "broader implications and consequences of one's actions and choices", and the marginalized character o requires a renewed commitment to embodiment. education into every field of study [5]. The proposal to inculcate moral and civic values in higher education raises a number of fundamental but potentially controversial questions in terms of what constitutes character education, what its purpose is, and what needs to be done to achieve this goal in different societies.

IV. DISCUSSION

The moral development approach, the analytical approach, and the critical thinking approach are three related approaches. While each recognizes the importance of ethical reasoning skills, there are some subtle differences between them. The moral development approach is based on the assumption that people develop their moral judgments progressively from the current level to the next higher level. It focuses on personal ethical dilemmas and suggests incorporating structured and controversial ethical dilemmas into group discussions to guide students to make informed ethical choices. An analytical approach based on logical and empirical processes focuses on social values and emphasizes logical thinking

and reasoning in helping students use logical thinking and scientific inquiry[6]. In the context of English language learning in higher education, character education can play an important role in helping students become more effective communicators and global citizens. In this essay, we explore the importance of introducing character education in English language learning in higher education and the approaches that teachers can take to improve character education in universities. Incorporating character education into English language learning in higher education is that it helps students develop a strong sense of ethics and responsibility. By teaching students about the importance of honesty, integrity, and responsibility, teachers help them become more responsible and trustworthy individuals. This can have a positive impact on their personal and professional lives as they become better equipped to make ethical decisions and take responsibility for their actions. By teaching students the importance of treating others with kindness and respect, teachers can help them become more empathetic and understanding individuals. This can have a positive impact on their personal relationships and ability to work effectively with others in a professional environment.

V. CONCLUSION

Teachers can incorporate character education into their assessment practices. For example, they might ask students to reflect on how they have demonstrated ethical behavior or empathy in their writing or presentations, and suggest how they could improve in these areas. They can also provide opportunities for self-reflection and goal-setting, allowing students to identify areas where character development skills need improvement. In conclusion, character education is an important component of English language learning in higher education. By teaching students about ethical behavior, responsibility, respect, and empathy, educators can help them become more effective communicators and global citizens. By incorporating character education into classroom discussions and assignments, participating in service learning or community engagement activities,

and incorporating character education into assessment practices, educators can help students develop the skills and values they need to succeed in their personal and professional lives.

REFERENCE:

1. <https://www.graduateprogram.org/>
2. <https://en.wikipedia.org/>
3. Arthur, J. (2005). There-Emergence Of character education in British Education policy. British Journal of Educational Studies.
4. Harrison, T., Bawden, M., & Rogerson, L. (2016). Teaching character through subjects. Research Intelligence, 130, 14-16
5. Colby, A. (2008). Fostering the moral and civic development of college students. Handbook of moral and character education, 391-413
6. Huitt, W. (2004). Values. Educational Psychology Interactive. Retrieved August 3, 2020, from <http://www.edpsycinteractive.org/topics/affsys/values.htm>